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***Fratelli Tutti* from Biblical Perspectives**

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Abstract: Based on the Papal Encyclical, *Fratelli Tutti*, the author reflects on its relevance for today and applies it to various contexts like immigrants, inter-religious dialogue, political charity and peace and reconciliation. The author bases his exploration from Biblical perspectives and indicates the relevance of this powerful encyclical for our religious, spiritual, moral and political lives.

Keywords: Peace and Reconciliation, *Fratelli Tutti*, Immigrants, Good Samaritan, Good Politics.

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Fratelli Tutti is an encyclical. An encyclical is a letter circulated by the Pope to Catholic Churches worldwide. It is often addressed to all the people of good will who may want to read the document. Pope Francis' encyclical *Fratelli Tutti* (henceforth abbreviated as FT) is addressed to 'brothers and sisters all' (FT. 8). Papal encyclicals provide analysis, in the light of the Gospel and of the Tradition of the Church on relevant issues for the faithful. The topic given to me was "A Way of life for the New Year 2021 after Fratelli Tutti." Since this article was based on my recollection talk organized by Prerana, the Ignatian Spirituality Centre from Bangalore for the selective public on-line which is available on Youtube,¹ the style of this paper is conversational rather than technical. Definitely, you might have heard very many times this encyclical explained to you. But this is going to be somewhat different as I am going to look at each chapter of the encyclical from a Biblical point of view and will set certain guidelines from there, for our way of life during these coming years.

1. Dark Clouds Over a Closed World

Let us take the first chapter which speaks about Dark Clouds over a Closed World. Here I would like to bring to your attention the Foundational God Experience in the bible.

a. Dark Cloud in the Old Testament

As we know, the bible is divided into two parts: The Old Testament and the New Testament. In the Old Testament, the foundational God experience is the Exodus experience. What do we see in the Exodus experience? It begins with the call of Moses (Ex 3:6-14). Any call narrative has four parts: Whenever there is a need God calls. Then, he commissions. Then, the Prophet objects. Finally, God responds to the objection. When we come to Moses, first, God calls. What is the need for which God calls Moses? It is because that the people of Israel were languishing in

¹ Rathinam, Selva, *Prerana Retreat Talk 03*, Prerana Ignatian Retreat Centre. January 9, 2021, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sdZ9-J3F5II&t=9s> accessed on 08/07/2021.

Egypt as slaves. This is the Dark Cloud. God wants to liberate these people and for which God calls Moses. Then God gives a commission to Moses, “you go and liberate them.” But, Moses objected: “Lord, who am I that you should send me? Suppose the people to whom you send me, ask me, who is it that has sent you, what shall I say? What is your name? God responded to him: I am who I am, i.e., Yahweh! Then, Moses said, I do not know how to speak. But God responded to him saying, what about your brother Aaron and he can speak well and he shall become your mouth. This is the Call Narrative. But after listening to everything Moses said, ‘Oh, send somebody else!’ But, God told him, ‘I will be with you’ for this mission. In order to prove that God will be with him, God gave him three signs: God asked him, ‘what is in your hand?’ Moses said, ‘a stick.’ God said, ‘throw it in front of me.’ When he did this, it became a serpent. When he saw the serpent, he started running away. God called Moses and told him, ‘do not be afraid, come back and catch hold of the serpent.’ When he caught hold of the serpent it became a stick. Then, God told Moses to take water from the Nile and pour it upon the ground. It became blood. Then God told Moses, ‘put your hand into your cloak and take it out.’ His hand became a leprous hand. Again, God told him to put his hand back into his cloak and take it out. Now it became a clean hand. What is the meaning of these signs? In those times people were afraid of three things in Israel. Israel was a desert land and it was infested with snakes. People were afraid of snakes. Secondly, people were afraid of violence and that’s what blood. When they moved from one place to another, there was no police force to protect them. The robbers can barge in at any time, kill the travellers and take away their property. Finally, people were afraid of the dreaded leprosy. Therefore, we have serpent, blood and leprosy. They symbolize evil in Israel at that time. The meaning is this: yes, there is evil in the world, but God has

got power over evil. Thus, Moses was encouraged by these three signs. So, what do we see here? The Dark Cloud here is slavery! Then, God calls Moses to liberate these people out of this dark cloud.

b. Dark Cloud in the New Testament

Let us come to the New Testament. Here the Foundational God Experience is the baptism of our Lord Jesus Christ. Jesus came from Galilee and went to Judea to be baptized by John the Baptist at the river Jordan. When Jesus came to the Jordan where John was baptizing, he saw at least five groups of the elites. They were not stepping into the water but were just watching John baptizing. Who were in those groups? They were Pharisees, Sadducees, Zealots, Essenes and Apocalyptic. For the Pharisees, the Law was everything and if you obey the law, the Lord will bring the Kingdom of God. The Kingdom of God is the intervention of God in history. Sadducees were priests. They believed that if you perform the rituals well, then God will bring the Kingdom of God. Zealots trusted in the weapons and they believed in the power of arms. Essenes believed in the power of prayer. If you pray well, then God will bring the Kingdom of God. The apocalyptic had their Worldview. For them, this world is under the power of Satan. Satan controls the world through demons and demonic persons. When the fullness of time comes, God will destroy the power of Satan and will establish the Kingdom of God. When Jesus was at the Jordan, he saw all those elite groups and he rejected all of them. There was another group which was rejected by all those elite groups. They were the poor, the marginalized, and the underside of the history, the blind, the lame, the deaf and the dumb. It is those people who were standing in the water in order to be baptized in the hands of John the Baptizer. Jesus made a deliberate option for them. He went and stood among them. When he stood among them, what happened? The heavens opened, the Spirit of God descended upon him in the form of a

dove and he heard the voice saying, 'you are my beloved Son, in whom I am well pleased' (Mk 1:9-11). When Jesus made an option for the underprivileged, God seemed to have told him that he was dear to his own heart and he had made a right decision! Jesus stood with those marginalized people and there is one word which refers to those marginalized people and it is '*anawim*.' In Hebrew the word '*anawim*' comes from the word '*anaw*' meaning 'the bent,' 'the broken,' and 'the crushed.' The '*anawim*' are of four categories: the physically handicapped like the blind, the lame, the deaf and the dumb; the mentally ill people who thought that they were possessed by demons; the economically deprived people; and finally the socially ostracized people like the tax collectors, prostitutes, soldiers etc. These were the oppressed people. This is what the dark cloud during the time of Jesus Christ. Jesus had a call to liberate them. What did Jesus do? Jesus healed the physically handicapped, drove away the demons of the mentally ill, fed the economically deprived by multiplying bread and finally he accommodated the socially ostracized people and was even called to be the friend of the sinners and the tax collectors.

c. Dark Cloud in Our Time

Let us come to our country. What is the dark cloud here in 2020? On Jan. 30, 2020 the Covid-19 pandemic was confirmed to have spread to India from China. The first case of Covid-19 was spotted in Kerala in India. Janata Curfew on March 22 and immediately after a 21-day lockdown was announced by the Prime-Minister throughout India to prevent the spread of the Covid 19 pandemic. Millions of poor and jobless migrant labourers were returning to their homes hundreds of kilometers away on foot since public and private transport has come to a standstill across India. Instead of helping distraught citizens cope with these frustrating and

hungry times, many Indian police personnel were increasingly caught harassing and assaulting them.

Ever since the Modi government passed the CAA (Citizenship Amendment Act) in December 2019, there has been fear and panic around the country. Hundreds and thousands of people were on the streets to call for the laws to be rolled back. On February 23 riots broke out in Delhi between Anti-CAA and pro-CAA protestors. The violence took a communal turn and led to the death of over 53 people. Modi and his Party have chosen to dig in their heels and have refused to acknowledge the concerns of the protesters and have instead sought to depict the protesters as violent anti-nationals, as reported in the article “Delhi Violence” in *Scroll.in*, 22/12/20.

In September 2020 during the time of the pandemic the Parliament of India passed three farm acts. Many farmer unions described the acts as “anti-farmer laws” and many opposition political parties also said it would leave farmers at the mercy of corporates. In tens of thousands of farmer unions notably from Punjab, Rajasthan and Haryana protested against the three farm acts and marched towards the nation’s capital with a movement named *Dilhi chalo* (transl, let’s go to Delhi). Although several rounds of talks have taken place between the centre and farmers no solution is sighted till date.

Such insensitivity and lovelessness towards the suffering can be called the dark clouds in 2020. Now I want to ask you two questions: What is the Cloud of Darkness that you experience at present? If God sends you out as he sent out Moses and Jesus, will you be ready to take up the mission you are called for in 2021?

2. Parable of the Good Samaritan

We have three types of characters in this parable. The first one was the wounded man, perhaps he was a Jew because he was coming from visiting the Jerusalem Temple. The second one was the Good Samaritan who approached him. The third category was the people like the priest and the Levite, who avoided the wounded man. Why did they do what they did? The priest and the Levite avoided the wounded man because they asked the wrong type of question: if I go near the wounded man what will happen to ME? This is very self-oriented and selfish question. Suppose the wounded man dies I will be polluted, made unclean and disqualified to offer sacrifices to the Lord. This is the reason why they abandoned the wounded man and walked away. But, the Samaritan asked the right type of question: if I do not go near him, what will happen to HIM? This is the other oriented question. Since he didn't want to let him die abandoned, he opted for him. The word 'neighbour' comes from the word 'neigh' which means 'near.' Jesus asked the question, who was the neighbour to the one who was wounded? It is the Good Samaritan who went near him. Jesus gives us no choice here, either you take care of the needy or you do not take care of the needy. The Good Samaritan could have given other excuses: He is a Jew and I am a Samaritan and why should I help him? Or he could have gone either after the robbers or to the higher authorities to make a complaint. But, Jesus gives only two choices: Here are the needy people and when you see them what will you do? When we pay attention to the Good Samaritan we see that he took care of the wounded man. What is it that moved him to take care of him? In the passage it is said that when he saw the wounded man, he had compassion on him (Lk 10:33).

a. Compassion

This particular word ‘compassion’ is very important. In Ex 33:18-23 Moses wanted to see God and he expressed his desire to Yahweh. But God told him that no one can see me and live and yet, since you are my friend I will make an exception to you. Come tomorrow to the mountain top and there I will walk before you and will show myself to you. The next day, Moses went up to the top of the Mountain and was standing behind the rock. God was walking in front of him. At that time, these were the words which were pronounced: “the Lord, the Lord, a God merciful and gracious, slow to anger, and abounding in steadfast love and faithfulness, keeping steadfast love for the thousandth generation, forgiving iniquity and transgression and sin, yet by no means clearing the guilty, but visiting the iniquity of the parents upon the children and the children’s children, to the third and the fourth generation” (Ex 34:6-7). There are three words which give the character of God here: merciful, gracious and steadfast love. In Hebrew the word for merciful is *rahamim* which is translated usually as compassion. But, literally *rehem* in singular means the womb of a mother. Tony de Mello used to say that if you had asked Jesus Christ, who God is like, he would have said with a wink in his eyes, do you want to know who God is? God is wombish! The word ‘wombish’ does not appear in English but this is what the literal translation of the Hebrew word ‘*rehem*.’ A mother will never hate the child which is formed within her womb. She will always forgive the child. Not that after we have been born, she scolded us and hurt us, but what I mean is that when we were within her womb she chose to love us and allowed us to survive. This is the love of the mother. We were all formed within the womb of God before we were formed within the womb of our mothers. Therefore, God will never punish us and God will always forgive us. Even before we thought of committing a sin, God had forgiven us and we only have to appropriate this forgiveness from the Lord. This is the love of God. Thus, ‘merciful’ or ‘compassion’ means forgiveness.

b. Relationships

Secondly ‘compassion’ also is an action word. There are very many levels of relationships. In fact, the whole *Fratelli Tutti*, speaks about relationships. The first level of relationship is ‘hai bye’ relationship. You meet someone and say ‘hi’ and he or she says after sometime ‘bye,’ and sometimes, with this, the relationship comes to an end. The second level of relationship is speaking about the externals: you say ‘oh, it is going to rain,’ and the other says ‘oh, yes, it is going to rain.’ The third level of relationship is discussing ideas. Now we have come to the head and it is deeper than the previous levels. Then, the fourth level is giving expression to our feelings: ‘I feel sad’ or ‘I feel bored’ etc. Finally, the deepest level of relationship which is called the ‘gut’ level relationship and this is what ‘*rahamim*,’ ‘compassion.’ This Hebrew word ‘*rahamim*’ is translated as ‘*splangnizomai*’ in the New Testament Greek. ‘*splangnon*’ means ‘bowel’ or ‘entrail.’ In Mk 6:34 it is said that when Jesus saw the crowd in the desert, he had compassion (*splangnizomai*) for them, that is, he was moved at the deeper level, at the gut level, by bowels or entrails. Then, what did he do? He multiplied bread and fed the hungry. Thus, the gut level relationship does not remain only with feelings but it does something to the other in action. Very many places in the New Testament we have instances where Jesus had compassion on the people and in all those instances Jesus did something to them. When the father saw the prodigal son, it is said that he had compassion on him (Lk 15:20). Then, we ask the question, what did he do? The father put a ring on finger and put sandals on his feet. In Lk 7:11-17 there was a widow who was walking on the street with the dead body of her son. When Jesus saw, he had compassion (Lk 7:13). Then, what did he do? He gave life to the dead man and returned the son to his mother.

3. Love Is a Value for Us

We all need to have compassion to bring the people out of this Cloud of Darkness. This is what the Good Samaritan has done. Do we have this compassion within us? For us, Christians, love is a value. Love is actually a Trinitarian Spirituality: The Father, the Son and the Holy Spirit. How to understand the Holy Trinity? Let me share with you how the Lord enlightens me with regard to this. First of all, who is the Father? Ex 3:6-14: I am the God of your father, the God of Abraham, the God of Isaac, and the God of Jacob. I have come down from heaven in order to deliver the people from their slavery and take them to the land flowing with milk and honey. The people have experienced the love of this God through the burning bush, the ten plagues, the division of the red sea, the pillar of cloud, the pillar of fire, Manna in the desert! It is Jesus who gives name to this God in the New Testament as Father (Lk 11:2). Therefore, It is the love which the people thought that has come from above is the Father. Secondly, who is the Son? Who is this Jesus Christ whom we are talking about? For this we need to go to the gospels and see his life from Bethlehem to Calvary. In Lk 7:11-17, when a widow of Naim lost her only son, Jesus goes there and weeps with her. This is Jesus. In Jn 8:1-11 when a woman caught in the very act of adultery was about to be stoned to death, Jesus goes there and protects her. This is Jesus. In Jn 11 we see Martha and Mary who have lost their only brother Lazarus. Jesus goes there to the tomb and weeps with them. This is Jesus Christ. In Lk 19, Zacchaeus, a short man wanted to have a glimpse of Jesus Christ from the tree top, Jesus came there, called him down and went to his house to dine with him. This is Jesus. Jesus is the love which the people experienced WITH them. This love was walking upon the earth and miracles took place. Who did the miracle? It is love that did the miracle. Jesus is another name for this love. Finally we come to the Holy Spirit. When I reflect upon myself I see that I am finite. Before my birth I was nothing. After my death it looks as though I am going to be

nothing. Yet, I exist. Since I am finite, I could not have come from myself. The source from where I have come I call God. Who is this God? 1 Jn 4:7 says that this God is love. A steel chair cannot come from a wood. Only a wooden chair can come from a wood. So, if I am from love, then I too should be love. Thus, the more I become aware of my source I become love-able. This love-ability within me is the Holy Spirit. Rom 8:9 says that the Holy Spirit dwells within you. That's why, the personal prayer is very important in our personal life. Once I was teaching the diploma students, mostly the junior sisters in Jnana Deepa. In that group, I saw one of the students whose way of talk and smile reminded of another student whom I met in Jnana Deepa few years back. After the class, I asked her whether she knows that particular previous student. She said, yes, she was my Novice Mistress. Then, she told me that she was trained by her Novice Mistress for two years and she liked her so much that without her knowledge she imbibed her mannerism in her way of talk and smile etc. This is exactly the Christian prayer. St. Ignatius gives us what is called the imaginative contemplation in order to enter into the mysteries (the episodes) of Jesus Christ. Take one episode everyday for your prayer, become part of it, listen to Jesus, enter into conversation with him, see him, hear him and feel his presence and finally one day without your knowledge you will become unto the image of Jesus Christ imitating him and going out to others in love. Thus, the love which the people experienced from above is the father; the love which the people experienced with them is Jesus Christ and the love which the people have experienced within them is the Holy Spirit. God is love. If God is love, then, he cannot remain within four walls. Love needs the other. Therefore, God is a community. This community consists not of things but of persons, because, we use things and love persons and we should not love things and use persons. Therefore, this divine community consists

of the Father, the Son and the Holy Spirit. Since God is a community, community is a value for us. We all belong to one community or the other like family, religious community, club or guild. Do we facilitate the building up of the community or do we hinder the building up of the community? A genuine love will impel us towards universal communion (FT 95). When there is no universal openness in love, the abandoned or ignored brothers and sisters in our own community or country can become existential foreigners to us. “Racism is a virus that quickly mutates and, instead of disappearing, goes into hiding, and lurks in waiting” (FT 97). Since God is a person, person is a value for us. One may be poor or ugly or sick or old, yet, I will love him or her because he or she is a person. Today we need to recall to our minds all those persons whom we hate. Can we take a decision, now, right now to love them and forgive them, and only then, we have understood the Trinitarian God in our life. Christian virtue consists in not loving the lovable but in loving the unlovable.

Pope Francis uses the word ‘*ekstasis*’ in this particular chapter: “Since we were made for love, in each one of us “a law of *ekstasis*” seems to operate: “the lover ‘goes outside’ the self to find a fuller existence in another.” For this reason, “man always has to take up the challenge of moving beyond himself” (FT 88). What is this ‘*ekstasis*’? It has got two words: *ek* (out) + *stasis* (stand) meaning ‘to stand out.’ All of us have got the capacity to stand out of ourselves, to transcend ourselves. In love we transcend ourselves and reach out to others. Until and unless we become aware of this capacity to transcend in love we will not be able to come out of the wall we have built around ourselves. This is what the Incarnational Spirituality: Jesus, in the beginning, was the Word [in the heavens] and the Word became flesh [upon the earth]. So, Jesus transcended from one to the other, from heaven to the earth out of love for us. In the same way, we will transcend from ourselves to the other in love. This is what the capacity of ‘*ekstasy*’ in each one of us. We need to be aware of this.

So, what is this love? Love means ‘doing good.’ Pope Francis, in this chapter uses the word ‘*agathosyne*’ which is one of the fruits of the Spirit in Gal 5:22. This “Greek word expresses attachment to the good, pursuit of the good. Even more, it suggests a striving for excellence and what is best for others, their growth in maturity and health, the cultivation of values and not simply material wellbeing. A similar expression exists in Latin: *benevolentia*. This is an attitude that “wills the good” of others” (FT 112). This is the very same word, in Greek, similar to ‘*agape*.’ What does it mean? It means ‘using the determination of will to do good to others.’ Suppose there are two people in the community. One is the elder and the other younger. The younger one doesn’t like the elder one at all, perhaps, in the past the younger one was hurt by the elder. Now, both of them are watching a TV program. In between, the elder one gets up and walks out of the room trying to wipe her running nose. In the meantime, her kerchief falls down without her knowledge. The younger one noticed it and took the kerchief and gave it to the elder. Now, my question is this: has the younger one loved the elder one so much that she did something good to the elder? ‘No.’ In fact, she hates the elder one. But, by giving the kerchief to her, did she do something good to her? ‘Yes.’ This is what the New Testament agapeic love. It is using the determination of will to do good. This is nothing to do with feeling but with will. Jesus says in Jn 13:35: “By this everyone will know that you are my disciples, if you have love (*agape*) for one another.”

In the remaining chapters, Pope Francis points out to the target groups we must do good to. In the fourth chapter he speaks of the immigrants. In the fifth chapter he speaks of the political charity. In the sixth chapter he speaks of the

dialogue and social friendship. In the seventh chapter he speaks about peace and reconciliation with others. In the eighth chapter he speaks about the inter-religious dialogue.

4. Immigrants

Let us come to chapter four, the immigrants. Who are the immigrants? The immigrants are those people who do not have a conducive situation in their own place to grow and to develop and therefore they move from their place to another place. Whether they are immigrants or migrants or strangers, we need to accept them because they are human beings. In Gen 1:27 we read, “So God created humankind in his image, in the image of God he created them; male and female he created them.” In former times, only the kings were considered to be the images of God and the common people have to give dignity to them. But, in the book of Genesis, this idea of ‘image of God’ is democratized and applied to all human beings. Every human being is the image of God. God is in every human being and therefore we need to give this human dignity to everyone. Therefore, we need to give human dignity to the immigrants; the migrants and the strangers and we need to accept them. Then, Pope Francis gives the example of Gen 11:1-9 (FT 144) which deals with the tower of Babel. In this story we see ‘unity in uniformity.’ Here the people say, “let us make a name for ourselves” (Gen 11:4). It’s a kind of group or siege mentality. Very often we have such group mentality and do not allow others to get into our circle. In such group, there is no transcendence and it is unity in uniformity which is bad. In the Acts 2, quite opposite to tower of Babel takes place. Here the people seem to be diverse and they speak different languages. Yet, they all hear and understand perfectly the preaching of the Apostles on the Pentecost. Here, there is unity in diversity. In unity in diversity we are enriched and challenged. Therefore, we need not fear that we may lose our identity when we allow the strangers to join us. On the contrary, in their company we will be enriched and challenged. Then, Pope Francis uses the term

‘gratuitousness’ here (FT 139). What does it mean? Very often, when we see the strangers or the immigrants, we accept only those who are talented. But, Pope Francis says that we need to accept all of them, even the common people among them. This is what he calls ‘gratuitousness, that is, ‘gratis’ meaning freely we need to accept them. “Our response to the arrival of migrating persons can be summed up by four words: welcome, protect, promote and integrate” (FT 129).

5. Political Charity

Let us move on to Chapter five. It is on Political Charity. Charity is not only personal, intimate relationships but also macro-relationships which includes economic, political and social elements of the society having the goal of common good. Here, he speaks about the economic reality in the society. In order to have an economic strength, the nation should have two things: Capital with the business people and consumer demand. In very many countries, including our own, the government fills the hands of the business people with money exempting them from all sorts of taxes and obligations believing that they will start businesses and employ common people, so that the money will trickle down from the business people to the poor. But what happens is that money, instead of trickling down to the poor, going into the pockets of the business people. Quite opposite to this ‘trickle down economic theory,’ there is ‘trickle up economic theory.’ Here, the money is put first in the hands of the workers and it creates consumer demand. In order to meet the consumer demand, the businesses are developed. Thus, the money goes up in this ‘trickle up economic theory.’ The point of Pope Francis is that we should not be satisfied with any one ideology but need both the trickle down and the trickle up, keeping more importantly, the common good, in mind.

Majoritarianism, Populism, Concupiscence, Tenderness

He also gives examples from political life especially on majoritarianism and populism. Here is the government which is elected by the people. Once it is elected, the government should look into the needs of all the people. This is what democracy which is by the people, for the people and of the people. But, instead of taking care of all the people, what the government, most often, does is to take care of only that section of the people who voted for it. This is called majoritarianism. For example, when Fr. Stan Lourdasamy, SJ who was fighting for the rights of the oppressed Adivasis, was languishing in the prison without a bail, Goswami who was accused of crime against the nation, was released from the prison within a short time because he belonged to the ruling party. Similarly, the farmers are fighting for their rights for a long time, but the government is very insensitive towards them because it favours the corporates as it shares the trickledown theory. Pope Francis also speaks about populism which implies support for the poor and at the same time opposing the big institutions. Pope's point is that we need institutions also along with the option for the poor. Drawing the example from the Good Samaritan story, Pope Francis tells that in order to admit the wounded man, the Good Samaritan needs the Inn which is an institution. The point is that we should not be settled down to any one ideology. We must always ask the question whether it would serve the common good and accordingly we must make a decision. Pope Francis also speaks about 'concupiscence,' that is, promoting individualistic and selfish attitudes emphasizing, my community, my people, my language and my geographical area. It reminds us of the story of the Tower of Babel which lacks the dynamism of love element moving from one to the other. When Pope Francis spoke about political charity, he draws our attention to the social reality and in this context he speaks about what is called 'the tender love.' "What is tenderness? It is love that draws near and becomes real" (FT 194). He says that politics must make

room for tender love of others. For him, tender love is the love which springs from the heart touched by the smallest, the weakest and the poorest and reaches the eyes, ears and hands. For example, we live in a throw away culture where the people who are unborn are already thrown away by abortion and the elderly who are considered to be useless are thrown away by isolation. What Pope Francis is saying is that the suffering of such people should touch our hearts and sensitize us to their needs. Through social media often times we show our insensitivity towards others. Once the suffering of the people touches our hearts, the tender love will flow from our hearts to our eyes, ears and hands in order to take care of them. Therefore, Pope Francis wants us to keep alive within ourselves this sensitivity. So, what is this 'political charity' finally? Pope Francis advises us that we need to discuss about politics. In fact, before reading this encyclical, I used to tell myself what a waste of time that we speak about politics in our recreations and at table etc., But, what Pope Francis says here is that if we do not discuss and express our opinion on political life in smaller or larger groups, the other people who believe in certain ideologies will shape the society in their own terms. Therefore, we need to keep such conversation going in our day today life. We need to listen to the news, read the newspapers, get in touch with the signs of the times and enter into interdisciplinary conversation with others with regard to politics.

6. Dialogue and Social Friendship

In Chapter six, Pope Francis speaks about dialogue and social friendship, by which, what he means is that we need to build up the society together. In very many social networks when people are expressing their opinions entering into dialogue, in actual they are not in dialogue but in monologue, he says. Dialogue will take place only when we listen to the other.

When we hold on to our own ideas, then it is not dialogue. Reality is multi-dimensional and it cannot be looked at from different angles at the same time. If I say that the perspective from which I look at the reality is the only reality, then I make judgments out of prejudice, preconceived ideas and stereotyped views. We need to listen to others in order to build up a genuine society and this is his point. Recently, the Jesuits have emphasized what is called ‘the spiritual conversation.’ What do we do here? First of all, we pray over the matter which is given to us for reflection (that is, think about the matter in the presence of God). When we pray over the matter two things happen within us: we become interiorly free (which is technically called ‘indifference’). Here we distance ourselves from our own likes and dislikes; and we experience the movements of the heart (consolation and desolation). At the personal level what is it that gives me a prolonged peace (consolation) we consider it as the internal confirmation of the will of God. With this we come to a smaller group for spiritual conversation which consists of three stages: in the first round we share in the group what we felt in our prayer and this sharing requires ‘intentional speaking’ and ‘attentive listening’; in the second round we have a ‘reflective sharing’ of what we felt while listening to each other and in the final round we have ‘an open discussion’ to arrive at a possible consensus as the will of God. Then, if it requires, we come to a larger group for the sharing of our findings to arrive at a final consensus which is submitted to the superior for an external confirmation of the divine will. The basis of consensus is not relativism but truth and values (FT 206-208). Cultivating a new culture of acknowledging others can help us in this process of arriving at consensus. In this matter of consensus, Pope Francis draws our attention to St. Paul, who uses the Greek word *chrestotes* (kindness) in Gal 5:22 (FT 223). It describes an attitude of gentleness and not rude towards others in words and actions. “Often nowadays we find neither the time nor the energy to stop and be kind to others, to say “excuse me,” “pardon me,” “thank you”.... If we make a daily effort to do exactly this, we can create a healthy social atmosphere in which

misunderstandings can be overcome and conflict forestalled. Kindness ought to be cultivated; ... once kindness becomes a culture within society it transforms lifestyles, relationships and the ways ideas are discussed and compared. Kindness facilitates the quest for consensus” (FT 224). In the spiritual conversation I share what I feel and at the same time I remain free. Here what is important is the capacity to move from the head to the heart. Here, there is spiritual poverty, that is, I cannot know everything and I need the other. In spiritual conversation we believe that God has a mission for this world and he speaks through each one of us to draw us into this mission. Therefore, when we listen to each other, we actually listen to God and thus it becomes prayer. In the recent past, when I was the President of Jnana Deepa I made a suggestion to my Provincial that the administrative building should be turned into women’s hostel and the administrative set up can be moved into the newly built Postgraduate Block. The Provincial called for a spiritual conversation among all the Jesuit administrators on the campus. In the first round of it, only two people were convinced of the idea. Then with more information the group was asked to come back after two days with prayerful reflection for the process of spiritual conversation. During this time half of the group said that we need to turn this into the women’s hostel. Then, the Provincial asked us to come for the final round of spiritual conversation the following day. During this time, it so happened that unanimously we felt that we need to go for the women’s hostel and we concluded it. It was like a miracle for me! Therefore, when we have such spiritual conversation, it is possible to move towards the building up of the society.

7. Peace and Reconciliation

Let us come to the seventh Chapter. Here, Pope Francis speaks about Peace and Reconciliation. What is peace? For

Pope Francis peace is not the absence but it is the presence. Peace is not the absence of war. In the cemetery there is peace but this peace is born out of the absence of persons and that's not the real peace. In some of the Indian art, God is shown with *abhaya mudra* (the gesture of protection) which sums up the message of the risen Lord. Whenever the risen Lord appeared to the people, he said two things: do not be afraid; and peace be with you. Both are related. When we are walking on the road alone at night, we are afraid. But, when there is someone with us, we are not afraid and we become bold. Now, the risen Lord is within us and therefore Jesus says, "Do not be afraid" for you are not alone and I am with you. The awareness of the presence of Jesus within us brings peace into our lives and this peace the world cannot give to us. When will such peace take place in the Society? When we believe that each person has the presence of this risen Lord within him or her. Then, we will give dignity to each person. When dignity is restored, peace will be established in the society.

Then, Pope Francis speaks about reconciliation through forgiveness. Forgiveness is not forgetting, he says, but forgiveness is giving up my right to take revenge. You have hurt me and I have the right to take revenge upon you. Can we give up that right because vengeance belongs to God? When I was reading this, what came to my mind was the example of Graham Staines, the Australian Christian missionary who was burned to death in 1999 along with his two sons in the car. After his death, his wife made the statement: I forgive the killer. Then, someone asked her, what about justice in the court? She said that the law will take its own course. This is what forgiveness. Justice is there with the legal court but at the same time one gives up one's right to take revenge. We need this forgiveness to build up the society. In fact, the Greek word for forgiveness is *aphiemi* which means 'breathe out,' 'exhale,' and 'empty.' Suppose, you have hurt me, and I swallow up the hurt feeling within me. Is it forgiveness? No. The hurt feeling will become an acid within me corroding all my

interior parts creating ulcer and cancer and this is not forgiveness. Forgiveness is emptying and exhaling. Forgiveness heals us; forgiveness makes our prayer heard; forgiveness converts others.

First of all, forgiveness heals us. There is a book called, *Answers to Positive Thinking* in which the author narrates an incident. A young woman suffering from all sorts of diseases comes to the author for a cure. He prescribes the following. Take two buckets: one blue and the other red. Fill the red bucket with pebbles. Then, take the pebbles one by one and put it in the blue bucket. As you put the pebble each time relive the hurtful moment and pray for the person against whom you nurse grudge, and say, 'I forgive you, in the name of Jesus.' She did exactly the same. The result is when she emptied the bucket, she was completely cured. We are all wounded in one way or the other. When we forgive others we are healed from our wounds. In this our Master Jesus Christ is our example. The wounded Jesus even when hanging on the cross forgave the people who unjustly treated him. Can we say that his love transformed him and healed him completely that he rose from the dead like a new born child?! Secondly, forgiveness makes our prayer heard. In Mk 11:25 we read, "When you stand praying, forgive." Why does the Lord say this? It is because when we nurse grudge within our hearts, our prayer will not hit the roof and reach out to God. We need forgiveness for our prayers to be heard. Thirdly, forgiveness converts others. Once there was a woman who came to attend a charismatic renewal prayer session. There was no peace within her because she came for the prayer after burying her only young daughter who was raped and murdered by someone. The culprit was caught and was languishing in the prison. The preacher told her to forgive that man. After much struggle, she wrote a simple

letter to him saying that she forgive him completely and totally. To her surprise she received a reply from him saying, “mother, if you forgive me, I am sure that God has forgiven me”. Forgiveness converts others! There is a place in Italy where Maria Gorettri was stabbed to death, butchered like an animal by her own maternal uncle Alexander out of sexual passion. But the unyielding Maria Gorettri did not nurse grudge against her own uncle. She looked at him with love and compassion as she breathed her last in his hands. This had converted him. Alexander repented for his sins, even joined the religious order and died as a Monk! Suppose you have anger towards someone in your personal life, forgive that person from within your heart, and you will see that the forgiven person is completely transformed. Once there was a boy who was saying his family rosary. As part of the family prayer, he has to read out the list of the names of the family members for the blessing of God. While doing this, he omitted his brother’s name and his mother noticed it. His mother asked him, ‘my son, why have you left out your brother’s name?’ he said, ‘he hit me today.’ But his mother said, ‘don’t you remember that our Lord asked us to forgive our enemies,’ but he retorted saying, ‘yes, but he is not my enemy but my brother yet he hit me.’ When people who are very close to us hurt us, it hurts us very deeply. When we are hurt deeply what do we do? We avoid others. If at all we happen to meet, we either blame each other or in a denial mode replacing it with some other impersonal matter. But the Lord wants us to forgive. Once there was a father and his teen aged son. The relationship between them became so strained until one day the boy ran away from the house. The father realized his mistake, went after his son. After searching for a long time he put an Ad as a last resort in one of the local Newspapers in Madrid, Spain saying, ‘all is forgiven, come back tomorrow noon in front of the office of this News paper. We love you Paco.’ The next day when he went in front of the local office, there were 800 boys with the name of Paco waiting for their fathers to come and pick up!

In the very same chapter, Pope Francis also speaks about death penalty. Today there are ways to implement the law and therefore we do not require a death penalty. He also goes to the extent of saying that a life sentence also is a secret death penalty. When speaking about war, he says that always in the world, after the war, the situation is worse than what was before and therefore he is against the war, too. In the context of forgiveness, he brings all the above points.

8. Inter-Religious Dialogue

Finally, in Chapter eight, Pope Francis speaks about inter-religious dialogue. According to the Bishops of India, the Pope says that the goal of dialogue is to establish friendship, peace and harmony and to share spiritual and moral values and experiences in a spirit of truth and love. The interreligious dialogue can take place hierarchically or complementarily. ‘Hierarchically’ means ‘my religion is superior and yours is inferior.’ Here, dialogue cannot take place. ‘Complementarily’ means ‘yes, what I have not seen, you have seen and come, let us sit and share about this.’ In this encyclical, Pope Francis gives another idea of the interreligious dialogue. He gives an example from 1 Cor 12:13 “For in the one Spirit we were all baptized into one body – Jews or Greeks, slaves or free – and we were all made to drink of one Spirit.” What he means is that our body has got many parts, and all the parts of the body work towards the welfare of the body. In Indian Philosophy, there is a word for it: the welfare of the whole, the ‘*lokasangraha*.’ Now, there are different religions and they are like different limbs of our body. The whole body is like the society. The society has got very many issues. Each religion can offer solutions. Therefore, we, Christians, need to train ourselves in this. In Theology we try to give this methodology of theologizing on issues to our students. They go out for their weekend

ministries and during which they become aware of the issues in the society. When they come back with those issues, they were trained to look at them from the point of view of Scripture and the Christian Tradition. What does the Scripture say with regard to those issues and what do the Church documents say with regard to those issues? Thus, gradually we develop such a methodology and then share with the faithful and with the other religions. Then, the interreligious dialogue will become useful and beneficial to the society. Finally, Pope Francis ends by saying, “And in imitation of Mary, the Mother of Jesus, “we want to be a Church that serves, that leaves home and goes forth from its sacristies, in order to accompany life, to sustain hope, to be the sign of unity... to build bridges, to break down walls, to sow seeds of reconciliation” (FT 276).

Conclusion

In conclusion, I would like to add a note on combining the social commitment with our personal prayer life and it can be termed as Apostolic Mysticism. In the history of the Church, prayer life broadly went through three stages:² one in the fourth century where there were Syrian monks, called *Messalians* meaning the people who were always praying (1 Thess 5:17). They had a kind of prayer which was called ‘*theoria*,’ ‘*theo*’ means ‘God’ and ‘*horan*’ means ‘to see.’ They spent all their time in prayer elevating their mind to see the invisible God within and without. They were contemplatives. Looking at them people thought of two kinds of Christians: Martha, the people of the world, who work; Mary, the monks, whose duty was only to pray. Then, in the sixth century another type of prayer came with St. Benedict whose famous maxim ‘*Ora et labora*’ (prayer and work) was a refutation of those supercharismatics. Here, as in the Benedictine Monastery, people work for sometimes like Martha and come together to pray at other times like Mary. But, it doesn’t solve the

² Tomas Spidlik, “Ignatian Meditation and the Prayer of the Oriental Church,” in: *Ignatian Spirituality* (Roma: Centrum Ignatianum Spiritualitatis, 1979), 16-18.

problem. When I am absorbed in my daily work I simply cannot keep my mind on praying. Then, in the sixteenth century, St. Ignatius of Loyola came and introduced to us what is called, in the words of Fr. Lindworsky, the ‘School of the Will.’ What does it mean? The Ignatian prayer method supposes the unity of mind and body. This mentality seems to imply: “I know what God wants, and in the coming days or weeks or years I can do it.” Through such practice we purify our heart, and only the pure heart sees God. It is typically Ignatian to see God in my activity, to be a contemplative in action, to be Mary in Martha, not to be Mary at one moment and Martha at another moment. It is similar to what St. Paul says in 1 Thess 5:17 ‘pray always.’ How to pray always? St. Ignatius advises us to ask ourselves at any moment of our time: what is the will of God at this stage for me? Once I discover that this is the will of God, then, I put my heart and soul in doing it. When you are doing the will of God, you are praying. For example, I am teaching Scripture in the Theologate at Jnana Deepa, in Pune. What is the will of God for me at this stage? It is teaching Scripture. Once I know that this is the will of God for me now, then, I put my heart and soul into preparing and teaching the subject given to me. For others who are teachers, it may be Mathematics or History, doesn’t matter, when they are doing it well, they are praying. Tony de Mello has got two stories: once there was a little fish which asked the older fish, ‘where is the ocean?’ The older fish said that the place where you are in is the ocean. But, the little fish responded saying, ‘no, it is only water’ and it went away. Then the little fish put on the garment of a sanyasi, met the guru and spoke to him in sanyasi’s language: “Sir, where is God, I am searching for God everywhere, in the valleys and on the mountains. Guru asked him, ‘did you find God?’ He said, ‘No.’ Then, the guru told him, ‘Do not search for God, but just look and you will never miss God.’ Tony de Mello gives another story: there

was a guru giving classes to the businessmen. He told them that the fish taken out of water suffocates and dies. In order to survive the fish has to get into the water. In the same way if you are entangled in worldly affairs, you also will suffocate and die. Then, one of the businessmen asked a question: ‘does it mean that we have to abandon our businesses and join monasteries? The guru said, ‘No, hold on to your businesses but get back into your heart!’

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